

HeriTACE

Communication and Dissemination plan

Deliverable 7.1

Version N°1

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**Funded by
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Project information

Grant Agreement	n°101138672
Project Title	Future-proofing Heritage Townhouses by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space
Project Acronym	HeriTACE
Project Coordinator	Arnold Janssens, Ghent University
Project Duration	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2027 (48 months)

Deliverable information

Related Work Package	WP7
Related Task(s)	All tasks under WP7
Lead Organisation	Architects' Council of Europe - ACE
Contributing Partner(s)	LGI, UGent
Due Date	30.06.2024
Submission Date	26.06.2024
Dissemination level	Public

History

Date	Version	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Comments
03.06.24	1.1	Gloria Oddo, ACE	Pauline Assadi, LGI	
25.06.24	1.2	Gloria Oddo, ACE	All partners	

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Executive Summary

This Communication and Dissemination Plan is intended for the consortium partners to ensure their participation in all the related activities, and for the European Commission to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on the activities carried out.

The HeriTACE project places great importance on dissemination and communication, as they are fundamental to reaching out to different target groups and presenting research findings to them. The communication and dissemination strategy varies for each category of stakeholders, but the core message and brand remain consistent across all activities.

This is the first version of the C&D Plan, which sets out the overall strategy and planned activities for the successful dissemination of the project's progress and results. It shows the first steps taken in the first six months of the project, including: the project logo and visual identity applied to all project outputs to establish a recognisable brand identity; the production of a leaflet, and A0 poster and roll-up made available to the partners in the early phase of the project to support the project's identity and visibility during events; two social media accounts created on LinkedIn - with a focus on a professional audience - and X (former Twitter) - with a focus on a general audience. Other social media platforms might get added according to the project's needs and the content created. Targets and key performance indicators (KPIs) are measured within the report to monitor the performance of the strategy.

This document is meant to be constantly updated throughout the project's lifespan with the status and progress from the partners on their actual dissemination activities. The next version is due in M18 (D7.4), followed by a third version due in M30 (D7.5) and a fourth and last version due in M48 (D7.7). The final version will be submitted at the end of the project, as a final report on all undertaken dissemination activities.

The C&D plan comprises:

1. The overall strategy at different level and the roles to undertake by each project partners;
2. The C&D content;
3. The list of target groups relevant for the project purposes;
4. The channels to use to reach those target groups;
5. The social media strategy and type of content;
6. Report on the C&D activities until M6 on the F&T portal;
7. Annexes:
 - a. Visual Identity
 - b. Newsletter
 - c. Promotional materials
 - d. Press releases

Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F&T Portal	Funding and Tenders Portal (EU-portal)
GA	Grant Agreement
HEU	Horizon Europe

Glossary

Communication means 'Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. This means to:

- Reach out to society as a whole
- Demonstrate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges
- Strategically planned with pertinent messages, right medium and means.'¹

Dissemination means 'the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

- Circulation of knowledge and results to the ones that can best make use of them
- Enabling the value of results to be potentially wider than the original focus
- Essential element of all good research practice and vital part of the project plan'²

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

² https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en

1. 1. Communication & Dissemination Strategy

The HeriTACE project established different communication materials and tools to showcase its results to the main identified stakeholders/target groups, including: 1) policy makers, 2) building design & conservation professionals, 3) building owners, local communities and civil society, 4) building material industry and HVAC industries/SMEs, 5) the academic world in education and research, 6) companies/contractors specialised in renovation of historical buildings. A detailed list of the Target Groups can be found in chapter 2.

This chapter focuses on the specific roles of the project partners, then lists the public deliverables of the project - which are essential to disseminate the project on a broader scale. Thereafter the content, i.e. the target message of HeriTACE is presented.

While chapter 2 introduces the target groups and chapter 3 the channels to reach them, the overall strategy can be summarised as follows:

Online tools and channels to build an active community:

- **Project website** published in M6, which will be constantly updated with news, events, and general posts. The website is meant to be not just a simple archive of documents and activities, the website aims to demonstrate the feasibility of the holistic deep renovation approaches for climate-neutral historical neighbourhoods. The website takes a “marketing” approach by presenting its objectives, results, and key reports;
- **Social media channels** have been opened on LinkedIn and X-former Twitter since the beginning of the project. They have also been integrated into the website and are managed primarily by ACE and LGI, with contributions from all partners. A YouTube account has been opened to share videos on the project demos and overall objectives on a later stage.
- **A bi-annual newsletter** serving as a crucial media tool for informing the subscribers (partners and not) about the latest project news and driving traffic to the project website. On the newsletter the subscribers will find also relevant information and initiatives on heritage at EU scale

Events:

- At least **4 national and/or international events and workshops** to facilitate engagement with stakeholders and showcase project progress
- Participation in at least **12 conferences organised by third parties and EU initiatives** to communicate the project results at international/EU- scale conferences (e.g. in the fields of heritage, building energy renovation and energy systems, and HVAC), finding synergies with the EU institutions (e.g. EU sustainable energy week)
- **Clustering** and knowledge exchange are pursued between HeriTACE and FutureHIST, which are sister projects funded under the same call and topic. The two

projects have their own peculiar points of view regarding the renovation of existing buildings with historical value.

Publications:

- Scientific publications will be produced and published in open-access journals and online repositories. Open-Access journals and repositories such as Zenodo will be used. Partners' repositories will also be used to make publications accessible.
- Guidelines for designers and architects will be also produced in a form of booklet by the end of the project, providing informative design guidelines related to the project in a visually attractive form.

Communication materials:

- **Graphic material** such as a leaflet, an A0 poster and a roll-up poster have been developed for partners to share in occasion of events, conferences, workshops. They are also available on the website in the digital format.
- **A project video** will be produced to communicate the project objectives and vision to professionals in the sector, and of course the general public.
- **Public Learning module** for students and young professionals will be produced to spread the knowledge developed during the project among students and young professionals. The content of this video module will expose the innovative approach and technical features that have been developed.

The strategy will be regularly updated throughout the project's life. Partners will play an active role in promoting the project's communication channels and content to increase visibility and reach.

1.1 Role of the consortium partners

The **ACE** is in charge of coordinating all dissemination and communication activities with **LGI** leading some of the tasks. ACE is responsible for the C&D plan, the social media accounts, the newsletters. With the support of LGI, ACE will also develop the guidelines for designers and architects during the last phase of the project.

LGI is in charge of the visual identity of the project, the website, the promotional material, one video to be produced during the last phase of the project. Furthermore, LGI will have a key role in aligning the C&D activities with the exploitation strategy, which will be developed by **Polimi** in collaboration with UGENT and LGI.

Coordinator **UGENT's** main role is to ensure the scientific and technical quality of communication and dissemination activities. The coordinator also has the final say on the C&D material (both offline and online). Moreover, UGENT will organise cluster activities to increase synergies between and the visibility of Horizon Europe and European Commission-supported actions

TalTech, in collaboration with **SINTEF**, **Sakret OU** and **DENYS** will have a major role in developing energy-efficient and durable building envelope solutions for heritage buildings in three phases: 1) matching technical solutions for heritage buildings considering the heritage value and physical behaviour; 2) development of façade retrofit solutions that reduce heat losses while safeguarding the hygrothermal performance and reduce maintenance; 3) quantify airtightness levels for case-study typologies, and develop improved fenestration systems.

UGENT, TalTech, EURAC, ZH will optimise the comfort and IAQ in heritage townhouses in an energy-efficient way by developing and demonstrating smart HVAC concepts that safeguard the heritage value of townhouses; simulation-based design guidelines for optimal holistic renovation of heritage townhouses, balancing their heritage value with envelope and HVAC interventions, reducing the design cost in future projects; a set of optimised holistic renovation concepts for the heritage case studies with quantified performance.

KU Leuven, ZH, Builtwins BV, SWECO Belgium, SWECO Finland will propose clean energy supply concepts for historical buildings and neighbourhoods to investigate, develop, demonstrate and validate smartly controlled Renewable & Residual Energy Sources (R²ES)-based energy supply and exchange solutions for historical buildings, in line with heritage constraints.

UGent, SINTEF, NIKU, PoliMi, City of Ghent and **MKA** will develop a holistic and multi-scale renovation approach for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods and validate a multi-dimensional assessment model for identifying the most appropriate deep energy retrofit solutions.

All partners are expected to actively participate in communication and dissemination activities by contributing to the project's newsletters, providing updates for the website and social media, and bring the promotional material at their own events and conferences. They will also help spread the content through their own dissemination networks, channels, and networks.

1.2 Relationship with the other project activities

Dissemination and communication are closely tied to all other project activities and progress, as they continuously contribute to all communication efforts, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 - Connection among the different WPs

As the project activities are interconnected with C&D, all public deliverables produced during the project will be indeed used to create dissemination content that reaches the target groups. The following table lists all the project deliverables with a public dissemination level, including the partners leading and the due date.

Deliverable n.	Title	Responsible partner	Type	Due date
D1.1	Project Management Plan	UGent	R – Document, report	M3
D1.2	Data Management Plan (initial)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M6
D1.3	Data Management Plan (update)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M30
D1.4	Data Management Plan (final)	UGent	DMP – Data Management Plan	M48
D2.1	Building envelope characteristics	TalTech	R – Document, report	M12
D2.2	Energy Conservation measures inventory	TalTech	R – Document, report	M12
D2.4	Future-proof concept for interior retrofitting of wooden facades	SINTEF	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M30
D2.5	Improved historical window systems	UGent	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M24
D3.1	HVAC-concepts for heritage buildings	ZH	R – Document, report	M12

D3.2	Comfort and IAQ in heritage townhouses	ZH	R – Document, report	M18
D3.3	Baseline BES-models	UGent	Other	M24
D3.4	Smart ventilation strategies reducing moisture risks	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M36
D3.5	Performance-based ventilation and control strategies	UGent	R – Document, report	M36
D3.6	Ventilative cooling guide	EURAC	R – Document, report	M30
D3.7	Smart hybrid heating concepts	UGent	R – Document, report	M36
D3.8	Performance assessment of building envelope and HVAC concepts in heritage townhouses (initial)	UGent	R – Document, report	M40
D3.9	Performance assessment of building envelope and HVAC concepts in heritage townhouses (final)	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D4.1	R ² ES-based energy supply concepts for heritage buildings in historical neighbourhoods	SWECO Finland	R – Document, report	M12
D4.3	Feasibility of heat recovery from unharvested local sources in heritage environments	SWECO Belgium	R – Document, report	M24
D4.4	GPU-based MPC solver	Builtwins BV	R – Document, report	M36
D4.5	MPC demonstration in historic building	Builtwins BV	R – Document, report	M36
D4.6	Building block MPC extensions	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M42
D4.7	Performance assessment of R ² ES concepts in heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods (initial)	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M40
D4.8	Performance assessment of R ² ES concepts in heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods (final)	KU Leuven	R – Document, report	M48
D5.1	Case-study selection at building and neighbourhood levels	UGent	R – Document, report	M6
D5.2	Cultural heritage analysis and value assessment	NIKU	R – Document, report	M18
D5.3	Cultural heritage building user and owner perspectives	NIKU	R – Document, report	M18

D5.4	Baseline scenarios	UGent	R – Document, report	M18
D5.5	Map of KPI	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M18
D5.6	Visualisation model to assess the visual impact of energy retrofitting solutions on the building heritage value	SINTEF	Other	M30
D5.7	Multidimensional model for the holistic and multi-scale assessment of heritage buildings	SINTEF	R – Document, report	M36
D5.8	Validation of the holistic and multi-scale assessment model	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D6.1	Transdisciplinary processes for the holistic future-proofing of heritage buildings in neighbourhoods	POLIMI	R – Document, report	M48
D6.2	Policy advice report	POLIMI	R – Document, report	M48
D6.3	Customer services for early-stage design of neighbourhood energy systems	SWECO Finland	R – Document, report	M48
D6.4	Integrated and balanced design guidelines for heritage townhouses	UGent	R – Document, report	M48
D6.5	Early design tools for the feasibility assessment of innovative HVAC and energy solutions	SWECO Belgium	R – Document, report	M48
D6.6	Technical guidelines for building the building envelope solutions	TalTech	R – Document, report	M42
D7.1	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 1)	ACE	R – Document, report	M6
D7.2	HeriTACE Visual Identity	LGI	Other	M6
D7.3	Website and social media	LGI	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M6
D7.4	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 2)	ACE	R – Document, report	M18
D7.5	Communication and Dissemination plan (version 3)	ACE	R – Document, report	M30
D7.6	Online and offline dissemination material (version 1)	ACE	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M30
D7.7	Communication and Dissemination plan (final version)	ACE	R – Document, report	M48

D7.8	Online and offline dissemination (version 2) and offline material	ACE	DEC –Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M48
D7.9	Guidelines for designers and architects	ACE	R – Document, report	M48

Table 1 - List of public deliverables

From the deliverables mentioned in this table, D1.1, D1.2, D5.1, D7.1, D7.2, and D7.3 will be uploaded on the website in the upcoming weeks as they are due in M6 (June 2024).

1.3 Key messages for C&D

HeriTACE project proposes innovative solutions to future-proof heritage townhouses and historical neighbourhoods in three EU climate zones in a holistic way while preserving their heritage value. These solutions include a holistic assessment model and replicable optimal design approaches for the deep renovation of heritage townhouses. The integrated approaches are supported by innovations involving durable insulation and air tightness solutions, optimised and smart HVAC concepts and integrated R²ES-based energy supply solutions for historical buildings and neighbourhoods.

The following key messages have been developed to address different types of audiences, including the general public. They are used on the website and other communication tools such as online and offline promotional materials (leaflet, A0 poster, roll-up poster).

1.3.1 Key message (long version)

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

HeriTACE is a collaborative initiative aimed at transforming heritage townhouse buildings into energy-efficient assets while preserving their historical integrity. Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighbourhoods. Join us in realizing the EU Green Deal and New European Bauhaus objectives by navigating the future of heritage conservation and energy efficiency.

Holistic and multi-scale approach

The HeriTACE project addresses the complex challenge of transitioning historical European cities towards climate neutrality while preserving their cultural heritage and identity. Its mission is to create a sustainable, inclusive living environment in alignment with the EU Green Deal and New European Bauhaus.

Objectives

- *Develop a replicable holistic assessment model to evaluate the heritage value of historical townhouses and the impact of energy retrofit measures.*
- *Develop optimal and integrated design approaches for deep renovation of heritage townhouses within historical neighbourhoods.*
- *Provide durable insulation and air tightness solutions for building envelope renovation, respecting heritage values and traditional building technology*
- *Develop optimized and smart-controlled HVAC concepts to improve comfort and indoor air quality in historical townhouses, reducing energy demand by 60%.*
- *Develop integrated R²ES-based energy supply solutions, maximising the share of local R²ES in heritage buildings within historical neighbourhoods and promote collective energy supply systems on a neighbourhood level, where feasible.*
- *Vision for Sustainability: HeriTACE aims to develop a balanced vision and plan for heritage buildings and neighbourhoods, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals, and providing transition roadmaps and policies.*
- *Deep Renovation Challenges: The project addresses sub-optimal renovation practices, especially for historical buildings, by advocating for efficient and standardized approaches to ensure coordinated work execution.*
- *Energy Efficiency and Integration: HeriTACE focuses on significant energy demand reduction and local Renewable and Residual Energy Sources (R²ES) integration, addressing challenges in applying energy-efficient (collective) technologies and improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).*
- *Holistic Approach: Emphasizing physically sound and durable insulation solutions, optimization of HVAC systems, and aesthetically integrated R²ES solutions at the neighbourhood level to enhance efficiency and inclusivity.*
- *Collaborative Solutions: HeriTACE promotes collaboration among stakeholders to develop high-quality solutions for heritage conservation, aiming to deliver replicable models and standards for sustainable energy transitions in historical neighbourhoods.*

1.3.2 Key message (short version)

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighbourhoods.

2. Target groups and KPIs

As previously mentioned in the C&D strategy (chapter 1), the following target groups have been identified as essential for the success of the HeriTACE project:

Figure 2 - HeriTACE main target groups

Table 2 gives an overview of the communication tools and channels that will be adapted to each target audience. Quantified targets have been set to measure the impact and evaluate the effectiveness of the project's main communication and dissemination tools and channels. If the targets listed are not achieved, corrective actions will be implemented to ensure success and reported on the next version of the C&D plan.

Channel	Purpose	Target audience	KPIs	Impacts of KPIs
Project website	Main channel. Provide project information and latest updates in an interactive & user-friendly format	All target audiences, general public	10 000 visits by the end of the project	Wide scale dissemination of project key messages, public results & news.
Social media (Twitter and LinkedIn)	Provide project updates, news and insights and build an online community	All target audiences (Twitter mostly for the general public; LinkedIn mostly for professionals)	Combined number of followers 650	Increased awareness of the importance of historical building renovations; Engagement of stakeholders & dissemination of key results

Newsletters	Inform stakeholders of project progress, news & events of interest	All target audiences	150 subscribers by the end of the project	Dissemination and increased awareness of project results
National and/or international events and workshops / EU projects	Facilitate engagement with stakeholders and showcase project progress	Policy Makers, Building Design and Renovation Professionals, The Academic world - Education and Research, companies	4 workshops or project events (20-30 attendees)	Increased awareness and increased engagement with stakeholders
Guidelines for designers and architects (booklet)	Provide informative design guidelines related to the project in a visually attractive way.	specialized in renovation of historical buildings/ contractors, Building Material Industry and HVAC Industry/SMEs	400 views by M36	Increased understanding of new methods and tools for historical building renovation; dissemination of guidelines from the project's results
Scientific publications and non-scientific (technical/ specialist journals, newsletters)	Communicating the project results to the scientific community, Publications via ICOMOS, WTA Int., ACE, REHVA, Eurocities, Energy-cities, culturalheritageinaction.eu, historic-towns, Europa Nostra, BuildUP		at least 10 open access scientific publications/ at least 8 newsletter items	Sharing knowledge of new methods and tools for historical building renovation with the scientific and R&D community and Academia.
Participation in conferences organised by third parties and EU initiatives	Communicating the project results at international/EU-scale conferences (e.g. in the fields of heritage, building energy renovation and energy systems, HVAC), finding synergies with the EU institutions (e.g. EU sustainable energy week)		Project represented in at least 12 conferences, EC initiatives and events, commercial fairs	Increased awareness and increased engagement with stakeholders and networking opportunities
Project video	Communicating the project objectives and vision to professionals in the	All target audiences.	At least 250 views	Wide scale dissemination of project objectives and outcomes

	sector but also general public			
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Table 2 - List of channels, target groups and KPIs

Besides the key target groups and the general public, the HeriTACE established an Advisory Board that will play an important role in supporting the research outcomes. The AB members are professionals in the field of heritage and energy efficiency in buildings, and they are representatives from the following institutions:

- The Flanders Heritage Agency (Agentschap Onroerend Erfgoed), agency of the Flemish Government;
- The Lombardy Heritage Agency - Italian Ministry of Culture;
- The University of Cincinnati;
- Renson, a Belgian-based company creating innovative products & concepts for a healthy & comfortable indoor climate.

3. Website and social media

Various C&D channels ensure a good visibility of the project towards the identified target groups and general public. These include the HeriTACE Website, the social media accounts (LinkedIn and X), the bi-annual newsletter, the HeriTACE Zenodo community.

3.1 HeriTACE Website

The HeriTACE website was online under the form of a landing page during the first months of the project, while waiting for its full development (figure 3 and 4).

Figure 3 - Website under development

Figure 4 - Website under development

The full version of the website has been launched in June 2024 (figure 5).

The website is structured into the following main pages and subpages:

- **Homepage**, giving a glimpse of the project and the case studies, countries/ climate zones, and duration, and containing the form to subscribe to the project newsletter and a preview of the news and events;
- **About**, containing further information on the project, the consortium, and the related initiatives and projects (such as the sister project FutureHIST and other HEU projects involving heritage buildings);
- **Heritage townhouses within historical neighbourhoods.**, which will provide more information on the typologies of buildings and neighbourhoods selected as case studies in the future months;
- **Resources**, including the public deliverables and publications, as well as the promotional material;
- **News and event**, containing all events and initiatives in which the HeriTACE project will be involved;

The header displays three icons linking to LinkedIn, X, and the project email. Furthermore, a footer on all pages showcases the EU flag and a disclaimer indicating the project GA number.

The website had 417 visitors since its launch, with the most visited pages being Home (90), Media Centre (68), The project (64). Users come mainly from the USA, Belgium, France, Germany, The Netherlands.

The screenshot shows the HeriTACE website homepage. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'ABOUT', 'HERITAGE TOWNHOUSES', 'RESOURCES', and 'NEWS & EVENTS', along with social media icons for X, LinkedIn, and Email. The main header features the HeriTACE logo and the title: 'Future-proofing Heritage Buildings by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space'. Below this is a large image of historic townhouses. A central text block describes the team's mission: 'Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods.' Below the text are three statistics: 17 Partners, 6 Countries, and 48 Months, each in a rounded square. A 'Learn more' button is positioned below these statistics. The bottom section is titled 'Our cities' and features a large image of Mantova, Italy, with the word 'MANTOVA' overlaid in large, bold, orange letters. A progress indicator with four dots (the first is orange) is visible at the bottom of the image.

Figure 5 - Website homepage after its publication

The screenshot shows the HeriTACE website with the following sections:

- The Project:** A header image showing a row of historic townhouses with red roofs and chimneys.
- Our Mission:** A text block explaining the project's goal to transform heritage townhouses into energy-efficient assets while preserving their historical integrity. It mentions the EU Green Deal and the European Bauhaus.
- Objectives:** Five icons representing different objectives:
 - Develop a holistic model and standard processes for renovating heritage townhouses in historical areas.
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 - Develop a holistic model and standard processes for renovating heritage townhouses in historical areas.
- General Information:** An aerial view of a city center with a list of key project points:
 - Value for Sustainability:** HeriTACE aims to develop a balanced vision and plan for heritage buildings and neighborhoods, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals, and providing clearer heritage and policies.
 - Deep Renovation Challenge:** The project addresses sub-optimal renovation practices required for historic buildings by developing for efficient and standardized approaches to ensure coordinated execution of works.
 - Energy Efficiency and Integration:** HeriTACE focuses on significant energy demand reduction and the integration of local renewable and flexible energy sources (RES) addressing challenges in applying energy-efficient technologies and improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).
 - Holistic Approach:** Emphasizing physically sound and durable insulation solutions, optimization of HVAC systems, and aesthetically integrated HVAC solutions at the neighborhood level to enhance efficiency and comfort.
 - Collaborative Solutions:** HeriTACE promotes collaboration among stakeholders to develop high-quality solutions for heritage conservation, along to other existing models and standards for a sustainable energy transition in historical neighborhoods.
- Our Consortium:** Logos for partner institutions: NIJKU, POLITECNICO MILANO, ghent, GENT UNIVERSITY, TAL TECH, KU, IGI, SWELT, SAKRETT, DENYS, and others.
- Subscribe to HeriTACE news:** A red button at the bottom of the page.

Figure 6 - Webpage on the project objectives and general information

Figure 7 - Webpage on the Consortium

Figure 8 - Webpage on the HeriTACE network (sister and related projects, related initiatives)

Figure 9 - Heritage Townhouses webpage

Figure 10 - Reports webpage

Figure 11 - News & Events webpage

Figure 12 - Media Centre webpage

3.2 HeriTACE bi-annual newsletter

The newsletter has been set up on Mailchimp and is meant to be sent out every six months to promote the project's achievements, events, and publications, as well as EU-scale initiatives relevant to the HeriTACE audience (call for papers, conferences on heritage buildings, EC policies on cultural heritage).

The first newsletter was sent out in June 2024 (M6 - figure 13). Unfortunately, the number of subscribers is currently low (26 subscribers) as it was possible to promote it only when the website was fully online (M6 - beginning of June 2024). In the next months, we will launch an 'Introducing the partners' campaign on social media, inviting users to visit the website and subscribe to the project newsletter. The KPI to reach for newsletter subscribers is 150 people.

[View this email in your browser](#)

Figure 13 - HeriTACE Newsletter #1

3.3 HeriTACE LinkedIn account

The HeriTACE LinkedIn profile has 136 followers (June 2024), including architects, engineers, experts in energy efficiency, experts in heritage buildings, researchers, and representatives for the EC. In the last six months, the page has had 176 unique visitors, 518 page views, and 4,429 overall impressions.

The KPI for social media channels is set for a combined number of 650 followers, so we are confident that we will reach this target by the end of the project.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/heritace/>

The screenshot displays the LinkedIn profile for HeriTACE. The profile header includes the company name, a description, and follower information. A recent post from INHERIT is featured, discussing the launch of a Social Lab for cultural heritage buildings. The right sidebar contains recommendations for other pages and people to follow.

Figure 14 - HeriTACE LinkedIn page

Figure 15 - Example of successful post on LinkedIn

3.4 HeriTACE X account

The HeriTACE X account has 51 followers, including H2020/HEU projects. In the last 28 days, the page has reached 14 impressions and an engagement rate of 3,4%.

The consideration about the LinkedIn KPIs can be applied to X, with the target being the total number of followers of LinkedIn and X combined.

<https://x.com/HeriTACEproject>

Figure 16 - HeriTACE X (former Twitter) account

Figure 17 - Example of successful post on X (former Twitter)

3.5 HeriTACE Zenodo Community

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is an open repository for all scholarship, enabling researchers from all disciplines to share and preserve their research outputs, regardless of size or format. It is free to upload and free to access, and it makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.³

The UGent coordinator has established a HeriTACE community page on Zenodo. This page will serve as a repository for the project's scientific publications and relevant reports, ensuring a lasting impact even after the project's conclusion.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/heritace/>

Figure 18 - HeriTACE Zenodo community

³ [https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide#:~:text=Zenodo%20\(https%3A%2F%2Fzenodo.org,regardless%20of%20size%20or%20format.](https://www.openaire.eu/zenodo-guide#:~:text=Zenodo%20(https%3A%2F%2Fzenodo.org,regardless%20of%20size%20or%20format.)

4. Activities reported on the F&T Portal

Every six months, regular reporting on the forecast of planned and undertaken C&D activities for each consortium partner takes place. All activities have also been reported in the F&T portal communication/dissemination section. A screenshot of this is included below, and it summarises all 12 C&D activities undertaken by the consortium partners from M1 to M6 (January 2024 to June 2024).

The screenshot shows the 'Project Continuous Report' interface. At the top, there is a progress bar with icons for various project metrics: Project Summary (red X), Researchers Involved (yellow warning), Deliverables (blue i), Milestones (blue i), Critical Risks (red X), Publications (blue i), Results (green check), Dissemination Activities (green check), Communications Activities (green check), Standards (green check), Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) (red X), Datasets (green check), and Impact (green check). Below the progress bar is a section titled 'Communications Activities' with a 'SAVE' button. A descriptive paragraph explains that communication on projects is a strategically planned process. Below this is a table of communication activities.

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status	Actions
ACE - HeriTACE project on ACE newsletter 02.24	HeriTACE Kick-off meeting featured	Industry, business part	Newsletter	reached around 16,000 subscri	Delivered	X
ACE General Assembly HeriTACE presented, 04.2024	During ACE General Assembly HeriTACE	Industry, business part	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	80 people reached	Delivered	X
ACE, LinkedIn repost about HeriTACE Kick-off 02.24	LinkedIn repost about HeriTACE Proj	Industry, business part	Social media	Reached 234 people	Delivered	X
ACE- HeriTACE kick-off meeting on LinkedIn, 02.2024	HeriTACE Kick-off meeting featured	Industry, business part	Social media	Reached 741 people	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI meeting 19.4.2024	Presenting project aims and first ste	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 5 people	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI meeting 7.3.2024	Meeting about district level RES pote	Local authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 4 people	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI seminar presentation 11.4.2024	Presenting project aims and first ste	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 20 people	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI seminar presentation 13.6.2024	Presenting Heritace project first ste	Industry, business part	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 60 people	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI seminar presentation 19.3.2024	Presenting project aims and first ste	Local authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	70 people reach from city plar	Delivered	X
SWECO-FI seminar presentation 5.6.2024	Presenting Heritace project first ste	Industry, business part	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 40 people	Delivered	X
Sweco-FI seminar presentation 12.6.2024	Presenting Heritace project first ste	Industry, business part	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet d	Reached 35 people	Delivered	X
UGent - HeriTACE LinkedIn post 02.2024	HeriTACE project start and kick off n	Civil society	Social media	1000 unique views	Delivered	X

Figure 19 - Communication activities reported on the F&T portal up to M6

Conclusion

The report outlines the overall strategy and planned activities for effectively sharing the progress and results of the HeriTACE project. Communication and dissemination are ongoing processes that occur at all stages of the project, rather than being a one-time effort. As a result, this document will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration to include reports from partners on their planned and actual dissemination activities.

All activities carried out by the consortium up to M6 (June 2024) have been included in this report. Additionally, the report includes details of the various dissemination materials and channels that have been established.

Being still in the first months of the project, it is important to ensure that the HeriTACE project is well-recognised and its results are effectively shared. For this reason it is recommended to all partners to use the visual identity guidelines and follow the strategy outlined in this deliverable. This involves correctly using the project name, logo, colour palette, templates, and acknowledging HEU funding.

Annexes

A.1 HeriTACE Visual Identity

Include elements from D7.2:

A.2 Leaflet

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses.

Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods.

A.3 Ao Poster

HeriTACE

**FUTURE-PROOFING
HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY
OPTIMISING COMFORT AND
ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE**

 heritace@ugent.be

 www.heritace.eu

 HeriTACEproject

 HeriTACE

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods.

An overall holistic renovation approach for heritage townhouses:

- Holistic assessment model and transdisciplinary processes to create a holistic vision and plans
- Optimal and integrated design approaches, replicable through standardised guidelines

Specific innovations for heritage townhouses in 4 historical cities:

- Durable insulation and air tightness solutions
- Optimised and smart controlled HVAC concepts
- Integrated local RES based energy supply solutions

 6 PARTNER COUNTRIES

 17 PARTNERS

 2024-2028

 4.5 MC BUDGET

 Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

A.4 Roll-up Poster

HeriTACE

FUTURE-PROOFING HERITAGE BUILDINGS BY OPTIMISING COMFORT AND ENERGY IN TIME AND SPACE

6
 PARTNER COUNTRIES

17
 PARTNERS

2024-2028

4.5
 M€ BUDGET

Our transdisciplinary team is dedicated to developing **innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods.**

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 HeriTACEproject
 HeriTACE

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A.5 Newsletter

A.6 Press releases

<https://www.sintef.no/en/projects/2024/heritace/>

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PROJECT

HeriTACE

A transdisciplinary project addressing the deep energy renovation of heritage buildings.

Contact person

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20. February 2024

The HeriTACE project brings together a transdisciplinary team of research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experienced in design, technology, and policymaking in the domains of conservation, buildings and energy.

A significant increase in deep renovations of heritage buildings has the potential to lead to effective energy demand reductions and readiness for the transition to Renewable and Residual Energy Sources (RES).

HeriTACE proposes innovative technical solutions, integrated into a holistic and multi-scale renovation approach, by developing and validating:

1. A replicable holistic assessment model and standardised processes to create a holistic vision and plan on the renovation requirements for heritage townhouses in historical neighbourhoods.
2. Optimal and integrated design approaches for the deep renovation of heritage townhouses, with well-considered, targeted and minimal invasive renovation measures.
3. Durable insulation and air tightness solutions for the renovation of building envelopes, respecting their heritage values and traditional